

Financial Constraints and Small and Medium Enterprises: A Review

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Key findings

We survey recent studies on financial constraints and the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Australia and the OECD.

- SMEs account for a sizeable amount of economic activity and play a critical role in the creative destruction process that generates productivity and innovation.
- Lack of access to finance is a major constraint on SME performance.
- Improved access to finance for SMEs is one of the most effective ways to enhance productivity and economic growth.
- Government programs to improve access to finance for SMEs have met with limited success

What we knew

- In Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) account for a significant part of the private sector and constitute 50 to 60 per cent of value added. SMEs have served as an engine of job creation and are seedbeds of developing entrepreneurial talent and innovation.
- Access to finance is often cited as an important factor in the survival and growth of small businesses. The lingering effects of the global financial crisis (GFC), persistent financial instability and diffused risk in credit markets put downward pressure on job creation and income security in Australia and many OECD economies.
- Policies designed to guide and support employment and competitiveness while preserving financial stability need to be based upon a knowledge of the effect of firms' financial constraints on employment, wages and growth. This knowledge will be key in effectively targeting interventions for firms whose success is held back by lack of financing.

What we do

- We review the role of small and medium enterprises (those with less than 250 employees) in Australia and other major OECD economies.
- We survey recent advances in the literature on the role of financial constraints for SMEs in the context of business cycles and economic crises, and the impact of limited access to financial resources for SME growth and development.
- We summarise and analyse the conclusions from the growing literature on the effect of firms' financial conditions on employment, productivity and wages.
- We identify the policy implication of these studies and make suggestions for policymakers aiming at addressing the financial constraints dilemma faced by SMEs.

What we know now

- The Role of SMEs: An OECD Picture
 - SMEs make up the vast majority of firms and account for a sizeable amount of employment and value added in most OECD countries. In Australia, small businesses are responsible for 44 per cent of total employment, 35 per cent of total Industry Valued Added (IVA), and 34 per cent of sales and services income.
 - SMEs play a critical role in the creative destruction process and generate spillovers to large firms and economy-wide productivity. However, in Australia most SMEs still have relatively low productivity.
 - Access to finance is cited as a key enabler of productivity-enhancing investments. The elasticity of total factor productivity with respect to financial constraints is larger for small, young and private companies compared to other businesses.
- SMEs and Access to Finance
 - Access to finance constrains SME performance because, without the ability to internalise financings need through capital re-allocation, SMEs rely primarily on external financial resources.
 - Due to information asymmetry in capital markets, the perception of risk pushes creditors to raise the cost of lending, creating a wedge between the cost of internal and external financing. Small and young firms are most affected as they do not have a track record that can mitigate creditors' concerns and thus face higher costs of external finance.
 - Unlike large companies, which are better placed to absorb cyclical fluctuations in demand, small businesses are more vulnerable to swings in revenue growth. This is especially true during economic downturns when business revenue decreases and the demand for external finance increases, and the potential lenders may charge even higher financing costs to compensate for the risk associated with economic fluctuations.
- Financial Constraints and SME Survival and Growth
 - SMEs' ability to effectively contribute to the economy with their unique advantages is conditional on firm survival. However, only a small fraction move onto a path of fast growth. In Australia, 24 per cent exit in the first three years, and only 39 per cent of new firms eventually reach the age of 10.
 - Improving the financial environment is the most effective way to facilitate businesses passing through the survival obstacles and growth restrictions induced by financial constraints. A developed financial service system facilitates the relaxation of financial constraints.
 - Financial constraint is more acute for SMEs planning to invest in innovative projects. The risks involved in innovation and the uncertainty of outcomes and doubts about the commercial success of the end product increase the size of the wedge between the cost of internal and external finance. This is exacerbated by the lack of complete appropriability of the returns to knowledge spillovers.
 - During the early years of existence, SMEs might be under-served by capital markets and formal financial institutions. Business owners rely on self-financing, borrowing from family members or friends, or trade credit, etc. In the face of severe financial distress, informal financing can save businesses from exiting. The reputation built in the informal financial market may contribute to successful financing in the formal credit market in the future.

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- SME, Financial Constraints and Employment
 - During the GFC, workers were more likely to become unemployed if they worked in sectors with high external financial dependence. This impact was more pronounced for workers in small and young firms and in part-time or casual employment.
 - The impact of government-initiated credit relaxing programs on wage and productivity are mixed. Research paints a heterogeneous picture of outcomes across countries.

What this means for policy

- In Australia, the share of loans going to SMEs has been gradually falling over time. This suggests an increasing number of small firms are financially constrained and struggling to grow.
- There are several areas where policy could improve the financial inclusion of SMEs:
 1. expanding the Financial Technology (FinTech) sector to reduce reliance on banks;
 2. credit information sharing; and
 3. modernising insolvency regulations and the legal system to support SMEs
- Risk-sharing guarantees have the advantage over other possible policies of providing SMEs with financing while improving the efficiency of market allocation and with minimal government interference and market distortion. Risk-sharing programs in Italy, Canada, Korea, Spain and France provide examples, however, most of these run a deficit.
- Government may play an indirect role in mitigating the difficult access to finance faced by SMEs. Government financial assistance in the form of subsidies or grants also improves the prospects of small and young firms in obtaining market loans and investment. Market assistance is easier to obtain because government assistance is interpreted as a quality signal about these firms. The KODIT initiative in Korea and the European Investment Fund provide examples of successful programs that could be adapted to Australian circumstances.
- Rigorous program evaluation must be a centrepiece of any new policies.

Where to now?

- The effects of SME assistance on wider economy aggregates remain unknown. There is a need to understand whether promotion of and assistance to SMEs is an effective way to achieve key economic objectives such as high employment or high rates of innovation.
- Heterogeneity of SMEs should be taken into account in program design.

More information

- We thank Diana Hourani for research assistance and the Australian Research Council (Discovery Grant 160101914) for financial support.
- Links to the
 - full working paper
 - the published version
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
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